

Democracy Lab Assessment

The team of the European project "INCITE-DEM – Co-designing democracy", co-funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe programme, is very grateful for your participation in the Democracy Lab! As we said, your opinion is important to us. Therefore, we would like to invite you to answer some evaluation questions about the Democracy Lab. Help us to improve this experience!

* Indicates a mandatory question.

1. What is your gender? *

Select only one option.

- Feminine
- Masculin
- Other: _____

2. What is your age? *

Select only one option.

- <20 years old
- 20-29 years old
- 30-39 years old
- 40-49 years old
- 50-59 years old
- > 59 years old
- I'd rather not answer
- Other: _____

3. **What is your completed education level? ***

Select only one option.

- Primary school (former 5th grade) / former commercial or industrial course / current 9th grade - 3rd cycle
- Secondary education (former 7th) - current 12th grade
- University education (bachelor's/master's/doctorate)
- I'd rather not answer

4. **Are you or have you been a member of any association or club? ***

Select only one option.

- Yes
- No
- I'd rather not answer

5. **Are you or have you ever been a member of a political party? ***

Select only one option.

- Yes
- No
- I'd rather not answer

6. **Before the Democracy Lab, had you ever taken part in a participatory democratic initiative? (e.g. citizens' assemblies, citizens' juries, mini-publics, participatory budgeting, etc.) ***

Select only one option.

- Yes
- No
- I'd rather not answer

Participation in group discussions and presentations

Answer by ticking how you felt during the two-day Democracy Lab workshop.

7. **1. I feel that I have been listened to and respected by the other participants. [Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think about the statement]**

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

8. **1.1 If you didn't feel listened to or respected, what were the reasons for this feeling? [You can tick all the options that apply]**

Select all that apply.

- The group didn't let you participate as much as you would have liked
- There was one member of the group who stood out and wouldn't let the others speak
- Because of your shyness, you didn't feel comfortable speaking in a group
- Other: _____

9. **2. I was able to share my ideas and opinions with my group. [Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think about the statement]**

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

10. **3. I think I was able to listen to the opinions of all the members of my group.**

[Tick between 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think about the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

11. **3.1 If you answered that you found it difficult to listen to the opinions of all your group mates, what was the reason for this? [Tick all that apply]**

Select all that apply.

- One or more person(s) would prefer to participate less
- The group wouldn't let the person(s) participate
- There was one member of the group who stood out and wouldn't let the others speak
- Other: _____

12. **4. I felt motivated and involved most of the time in the Democracy Lab. [Tick between 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think about the statement]**

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

13. **4.1 During the workshop, in the group work and presentations, there were times when I felt:**
[Tick all that apply]

Select all that apply.

- Bored
- Intimidated
- Pressured
- Valued
- Enthusiastic
- Other: _____

14. **5. During the Democracy Lab, I felt that there were times when I wasn't respected or listened to, due to some of the reason(s) listed below:**
[Tick all that apply]

Select all that apply.

- For my shyness
- For the colour of my skin
- For being younger than the other participants in the group
- For being older than the other participants in the group
- For being a man
- For being a woman
- Because I have more school education than the other participants in the group
- Because I have less school education than the other participants in the group
- For having more knowledge than the other members of the group
- For having less knowledge than the other members of the group
- Other: _____

15. **5.1. During the Democracy Lab, there were times when I felt:
[Tick all that apply]**

Select all that apply.

- Not listened to or discriminated because I had a different viewpoint to most of the group
- Pressured to decide in accordance with the majority opinion
- None of the above

16. **6. I feel that my knowledge and experience were important in the group work of the workshop.
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]**

Select only one option.

- 1 2 3 4
-
- Strongly disagree Strongly agree

17. **7. My confidence has grown over the course of the workshop.
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]**

Select only one option.

- 1 2 3 4
-
- Strongly disagree Strongly agree

18. **8. I learnt and acquired new knowledge about participatory democracy.**
[Tick between 1 - Strongly disagree and 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

19. **9. I felt more capable and powerful throughout the workshop.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

20. **10. Is there anything you'd like to add?**

Democracy Lab activities

21. 1. Looking back, I think that the activities before the workshop, using the sensitising booklet, were useful.
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

22. 2. The workshop activities made sense and were meaningful to me.
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think about the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

23. **3. The facilitation and moderation of the workshop team was adequate and well conducted.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

24. **4. We had adequate time for all the workshop activities (group work and presentations).**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

25. **4.1 If you disagree that the workshop was adequately timed, what changes would you make?**
[Tick all that apply]

Select all that apply.

- Less total time for the Laboratory
- More total time for the Laboratory
- Less time for group work
- More time for group work
- Less time for the presentations
- More time for the presentations
- Other: _____

26. **5. Is there anything you'd like to add?**

Specific activities in the working groups

Now evaluate the different methodologies and activities according to their usefulness and ease of use.

27. **1. For me, the preparation and sensitising booklet was easy to use.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

28. **2. The preparation and sensitising booklet was useful to me.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

29. **3. For me, the dialogue tool (computer simulation model) was easy to use.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

30. **4. The dialogue tool (computer simulation model) was useful for me.**
[Tick between 1 - Strongly disagree and 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

31. **5. The questionnaire on democratic innovations in sustainability was easy for me to answer.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

32. **6. The questionnaire on democratic innovations in sustainability was useful to me.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

33. **7. The experience canvas was easy to use in my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

34. **8. The experience canvas was useful for my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

35. **9. The timeline for analysing a local decision situation, with an example from Norway, was easy to use in my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

36. **10. The timeline for analysing a local decision situation, with an example from Norway, was useful for my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

37. **11. The democratic innovation wheel was easy to use in my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think about the statement]

RODA DAS INOVAÇÕES DEMOCRÁTICAS

OBJETIVO:
 É um instrumento de avaliação de processos participativos em contextos de inovação social, que visa identificar os pontos fortes e as áreas de melhoria de um processo de inovação social.

OBJETIVOS:

1. Avaliar o processo de inovação social em termos de participação, transparência, equidade, sustentabilidade e impacto.

2. Identificar os pontos fortes e as áreas de melhoria do processo de inovação social.

3. Propor recomendações para a melhoria do processo de inovação social.

APLICAÇÃO:

1. Pode ser usado em qualquer contexto de inovação social, desde que haja um processo participativo em curso.

2. Pode ser usado em qualquer contexto de inovação social, desde que haja um processo participativo em curso.

3. Pode ser usado em qualquer contexto de inovação social, desde que haja um processo participativo em curso.

4. Pode ser usado em qualquer contexto de inovação social, desde que haja um processo participativo em curso.

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

38. **12. The democratic innovation wheel was useful for my group.**
[Tick between 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

39. **13. The storyboard was easy to use in my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

40. **14. The storyboard was useful for my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

41. **15. Group presentations were easy to prepare in my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree on how you feel about the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

42. **16. The group presentations were useful for my group.**
[Tick from 1 - Strongly disagree to 4 - Strongly agree about what you think of the statement]

Select only one option.

1 2 3 4

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

43. **17. Is there anything you'd like to add?**

To conclude. A few thoughts.

44. **1. For you, what would be the best way(s) to have received reminders and information about the Democracy Lab and its activities?**

[Tick all that apply]

Select all that apply.

- By SMS (written message on mobile phone)
- By email
- By postal mail
- In face-to-face meetings
- In meetings on digital conversation platforms
- Other: _____

45. **2. Did you feel that you always had the support and clarification you needed from the project team?**

Select only one option.

- Yes
- No
- I'd rather not answer
- Other: _____

46. **3. Would you rather have worked in a single group throughout the Democracy Lab workshop? Or would you prefer to experience working in several groups?**

[Tick one option that applies most]

Select only one option.

- Only in one group
- In a different group each day
- In a different group for each activity
- Other: _____

47. **4. How would you like to continue receiving information about the INCITE-DEM project and its activities, such as the Democracy Labs?**
[Tick one option that most applies]

Select only one option.

- Through the project's social media in the internet
- Through e-mail messages / newsletters
- Through a specific group in a social media
- I do not wish to receive any further information about this project in the future.
- Other: _____

48. **5. Did you feel you learnt anything during the Democracy Lab? If so, what did you learn? Give us an example.**

49. **6. Did this Democracy Lab have any impact on you? If so, how did it happen?**

50. **7. Do you think that the debates and outcomes of the Democracy Labs that arise from your contributions have the potential to generate (political) change at some level?**

51. **8. How would you improve other initiatives like this Democracy Lab?**

52. **8. How would you improve other initiatives like this Democracy Lab?**

Thank you very much for your participation!

If you have any questions about this questionnaire, the Democracy Lab or the INCITE-DEM project, you can contact us at incitedem@ciencias.ulisboa.pt.